

Strengthening Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) To Meet Industry Needs in the Changing World of Work

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of Strengthening Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) To Meet Industry Needs in the Changing World of Work with reference to Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe-Oghara final year (HND II) students. The broad objectives of this study is to examine the potential ways of eradicating lack of skilled workers which causes poor quality of job performance and higher costs that can have a negative impact on the successful completion of job through the introduction of TVET skills. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Questionnaire items were distributed to 496 respondents to gather factual information about the topic. Their responses were tested using simple percentage and chi-square. The study found TVET skills played very important role in the 21st century job performance. Furthermore, it also shows that TVET institutions should restructure their learning curriculum towards meeting modern industrial needs; more effort should be placed on proper training of students by exposing them to practical training. This will enable them acquire the necessary skills required in the industry. The study therefore recommends that government should remove corruption and greed and formulate policies that will promote the success of TVET; government should assist TVET institutions by increasing the funding of TVET to enable such institution acquire modern equipment for the training of students.

Keywords: Technical Education, Vocational Education, TVET, Industry and Training

Introduction

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) is the education, training and skills development which is related to a wide range of occupational fields. This training is in skills and teaching of knowledge related to a specific trade, occupation or vocation in which equip learners with the required employment related technical and scientific knowledge and skills to become successful towards decent jobs and occupation (UNESCO, 2023). The technical education and vocational training (TVET) has globally been recognized as the most effective tool for increasing employment and poverty reduction. Vocational education and training, allows students to gain

practical experience in their chosen career path before they even graduate. Students who finish those Rigorous programs have the credentials and training they need to get started right away in their chosen career path According to Rimando, (2012) TVET is designed to provide the utmost development of the individual as a total person armed with technical vocational and academic competencies that will make the person economically established, responsible, law abiding, productive and competitive in the world of work. TVET focuses on the learning and mastery of specialized techniques and the scientific principles by providing knowledge and skills related to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life through formal, non formal and informal learning methods in both school-based and work-based learning.

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) has been recognized as the wide-diversified education system instrumental in making the remarkable contribution to economic growth of a country by a way of suitable training of youth to become self-reliant to the needs of society and changing technological work. According to Titus (2012) Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is known for its contribution to the much required human resources by cultivating appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes that would enable a nation to harness resources to industrialized and participated fully in the global knowledge. For Improved teaching and learning of TVET, adequate equipment, laboratories and workshop should be provided and utilized in the TVET programme. Provision of adequate career guidance to students of TVET should be encouraged to achieve their career goals.

Statement of problem

Acquisition of Skill is different from having vocational skills; as skill acquisition means the art of learning to do something in order to earn a living and or to survive. Thus, skills can be acquired from several sources depending on the skills and the environment. Acquisition of skills is different from vocational skills which is thus refers to skills and occupations that you gain toward becoming knowledgeable in a specific trade or profession. Acquiring one or two vocational skills is a vital first step to entrepreneurship. According to the U.S. Department of Education, technical schools teach the theory and science behind the occupation, while vocational schools take a more hands-on approach to teaching the skills needed to do the job successfully. TVET have the responsibility to harmonize these concepts but despite the detailed objectives of TVET and the efforts of TVET institution Nigeria youth still suffers unemployment and unemployable while those from a wealthy home are immigrating in a large number daily to foreign countries. How can TVET be strengthened to meet the Nigeria unemployment and unemployable youth in order to meet the industrial need in a changing world of work is the focus of this research.

Objectives

The broad objective of this study is to investigate the “current world of work”. That is:

1. Characteristics of the current world of work.
2. Contemporary equipment in today’s industries.
3. Contemporary technologies in today’s industries.
4. Contemporary collaboration systems and tools in today’s industries.
5. Survey Lecturers’ knowledge of these equipment.

6. Survey Lecturers' competence in the use of these technologies.
7. Survey Students' competence in the use of these technologies.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does the quality of TVET lecturer have on students performances?
2. How does the learning materials affect students knowledge on skill acquiring?
3. How does technical workshop and instructors handling skills affect student learning interest?
4. What relevance does TVET curriculum have with the present day societal need?
5. How does the cost of practical materials affect the learner's ability to pay?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the quality of TVET lecturer and student performances.
2. There is no significant relationship between the availability of learning materials and student knowledge on skills acquired.
3. There is no relationship between quality of technical workshop and instructors handling skills with students learning interest.
4. There is no significant relationship between the relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need.
5. There is no relationship between the cost of practical material to the ability of learners to pay.

Though this research work is centered around students of Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe-Oghara, it will be greatly beneficial to both TVET students and institutions both in Delta State and Nigeria as a whole.

Literature

According to UNESCO'S Strategy for TVET (2016-2021) in alignment with Sustainable Development Goal and the Education 2030 Framework for Action to strengthen TVET systems and advance youth employment, access to decent work, entrepreneurship and lifelong learning opportunities in specific national contexts, TVET is now challenged to improve on Skills development for decent work and livelihood which is a critical contributions to peace and stability; Developing life and work skills means equipping learners with relevant ensembles of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that learners can mobilize independently, efficiently, and ethically to solve problems in a global citizenship perspective.

Meeting industry need in a changing world of work focuses on improving skills several important activities related to skills development, anticipation systems and enhancing the relevance of skills development and strengthen the quality and reinforce training process in the field of TVET. Based, on needs and contexts of the changing world of work the need to review TVET policies through analysis and alignment of key policy areas such as sustainable TVET lecturer quality, availability of learning materials quality of technical workshop, instructors handling skills and TVET

curriculum to the present day societal need, and the cost of practical material, with the view to mobilize resources for the implementation of the TVET Strategy become very necessary

The Quality of TVET Lecturers and Students Performances

This is the effort to produce quality teachers in TVET and thus produce students who are multi-tasking and have a high level of readiness in career fields. The processes of ensuring that specified standards or requirements for teaching, learning, education administration, assessment and the recording of achievements have been met. Between students and students, students and lecturers as well as students and TVET college management has an effect on student performance

Availability of Learning Materials and Student Knowledge on Skills Acquired

materials allow learners to have practical experiences which help them to develop skills and concepts and to work in a variety of ways (Tuimur 2015) Instructional materials enhance the teaching/learning process by exhibiting information necessary to acquire knowledge and skills. Learning materials can significantly increase learners' achievement by supporting learning Atieno, (2023). With special needs may require more instruction time, other learning methods and professional knowledge. For example, an educational video may provide a learner with new insights and an appealing worksheet may provide the learner with new opportunities to practice a new skill gained in class. Farrant (2003) says learning is the process by which we acquire and retain attitudes, knowledge, understanding, skills and capabilities. Learning materials act as a guide for both the teacher and the learner. They can provide a valuable routine in the teaching and learning.

Quality of Technical Workshop and Instructors Handling Skills with Students Learning Interest

A workshop is a small establishment where manufacturing or handicrafts are carried on usually brief intensive educational program for a relatively small group of people that focuses especially on techniques and skills in a particular field. A workshop may introduce a new idea, inspire participants to further explore it on their own, or may illustrate and promote actual process practice. It is a great way to teach hands-on skills as it gives learners an opportunity to try out new methods and fail in a safe environment. The availability of equipment/materials influence students' technical skills acquisition the attitudes of instructors can arouse the interest of learners or otherwise, good instructors have several qualities in common. They are prepared, set clear and fair expectations, have a positive attitude, are patient with students, and assess their teaching on a regular basis.

Relevance of the TVET Curriculum to the Present Day Societal Need

An effective curriculum provides instructors, students, school leaders and community stakeholders with a measurable plan and structure for delivering a quality learning process. The curriculum identifies the learning outcomes, standards and core competencies that students must demonstrate before advancing to the next level curriculum must be integrated to portray the present situation. Integration focuses on making connections for students, allowing them to engage in relevant, meaningful activities that can be connected to real life. An integrated curriculum aims to connect the theory learned in the classroom, with practical, real-life knowledge and experiences

Vocational schools help with bridging the skills gap between work and education. Students do not enter the work field with little practical experience regarding the tools and environments in which they will work.

Cost of Practical Material and the Ability of Learners to Pay

Instructional materials serve as a channel between the teacher and the students in delivering instructions. They may also serve as the motivation on the teaching-learning process. It is use to get the attention of the students and eliminate boredom. These instructional materials bring life to learning by stimulating students to learn. The use of instructional materials in the classroom has the potential to help the teacher explain new concepts clearly, resulting in better student understanding of the concepts being taught. Sometimes this could be too expensive for some learners to afford thereby making it too difficult for them to cope with learning

Based on above literatures, the major three main learning theories were behaviourism, cognitivism, and constructivism. These theories are discussed in relation to how they can be applied to TVET curriculum to allow students to understand learning objectives.

Behaviorism focuses on the idea that all behaviors are learned through interaction with the environment. This learning theory states that behaviors are learned from the environment, and says that innate or inherited factors have very little influence on behavior. (WGU 2020) Every teacher knows that they will usually have a student in class who is difficult to manage and work with. Their behavior is usually hard to control and it can be extra work to get them to pay attention and stop distracting others.

Cognitive is a learning theory that focuses on how information is received, organized, stored and retrieved by the mind. It uses the mind as an information processor, like a computer Cognitive processes combine the acquisition of knowledge and skills with the ability to apply information to new situations. Alida,(2021) is of the opinion that Constructivism theory state that learners construct knowledge rather than just passively take in information. As people experience the world and reflect upon those experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into their pre-existing knowledge (schemas).

Factors that are Necessary for the Effective Implementation of TVET Curriculum includes teacher's training, availability of teaching and learning materials, time allocation, innovative classroom practices and integration of into other subjects.

- i. Instructor's training refers to programs, policies, procedures, and provision designed to equip Instructor's with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, approaches, methodologies and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community. This can improve teacher's knowledge, attitudes and readiness to offer expected knowledge to students. Training of teachers' can boost their confidence and ability to transfer knowledge and life skills to learners (Omondi, 2014) Teachers are the backbone of education and have the capacity to provide hundreds of learners with essential skills on daily basis as long as they are well trained on the curriculum and posses positive attitude towards the subject
- ii. Teaching and learning materials: instructional materials are critical ingredients in learning Instructional materials provide information and opportunities for students to

use what they have learnt. Without resource materials and facilities, the teacher may not be able to set the objectives that he would like his students to attain.

- iii. Time allocation for learning of practical skills: It is important when integrating practical skills into the curriculum that a specific amount of time be allocated to the practical skills and that it be clearly scheduled in the school timetable. Participatory teaching-learning methods, which are strongly recommended to teach these skills, require more time than classical teaching methods, as they may require more time.
- iv. Innovative classroom practices on the implementation of academic innovations refer to emerging practices that involve changes in what instructors and students do and learn in the classroom, which prepare students for lifelong learning in the information society. Examples of such practices can be activities that promote active and independent learning in which students take responsibility for their own learning, and activities engaging students in collaborative learning in which students work with others on complex, extended, real-world-like problems the curriculum responsibility of schools is to teach the skills and to serve as catalyst for the development of practical work that are based on the most current practical knowledge. In doing so, schools have the opportunities to make important improvement in the quality of practical skill education provided to students worldwide as a step towards improving global self sufficiency.

Method of Data Collection

In the course of this study, primary data will be used. Primary data will be sourced directly through administration of well-structured questionnaire (5 Likert Scales) to staff of Delta State Polytechnic, Otefe-Oghara.

Reliability Statistics

<u>Cronbach's Alpha</u>	<u>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items</u>	<u>N of Items</u>
.893	.902	15

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Questionnaires distributed

Options	Frequency	Percentage
No of questionnaire filled and retrieved	255	51%
Questionnaires not retrieved	241	49%
Total	496	100

Out of the 496 copies of questionnaire administered only 255 were filled and returned giving a 51% success rate. Thus, 51% of the questionnaires were retrieved while 49% were not.

Table 2: Sex of Respondents

Options%	Frequency	Percentage
Male	110	43%
Female	145	57%
Total	255	100

The table shows that 43% of the respondents were male while 57% are female 39% of the respondents are married and 61% are single.

Table 3: Department by departments' responses

Departments	Frequency	Percentage
Accountancy	59	23%
Business Administration/Management	74	29%
Banking & Finance	23	9%
Computer Science	26	10%
Science Laboratory Technology (SLT)	36	14%
Statistics	7	3%
Mechanical	13	5%
Electrical/Electronics	10	4%
Computer Engineering	7	3%
Total	255	100

Accountancy Department having approximately 23% followed by the department of Business Administration with 29% approximately Departments of Banking and Finance with 9% Computer Science 10% SLT 14% Statistics 3% Mechanical 5% Electrical/Electronics 4% and Computer Engineering 3% responses respectively.

Table 4: CHI – SQUARE STATISTICAL TABLE

FO	FE	F0-FE	(F0-FE) ²	$\frac{(F0-FE)^2}{FE}$
33	33.22	-.22	0.0484	0.00144912
47	44	3	9	0.204545454
11	11.22	-.22	0.0484	0.004313725
12	11.22	0.78	0.6084	0.054224598
10	10.35	-.35	0.1225	0.011835748
44	43.78	0.22	0.0484	0.001105527
55	58	-3	9	0.155172413
15	14.78	0.22	0.0484	0.003274695
14	14.78	0.22	0.0484	0.003274695
14	13.65	0.35	0.1225	0.008974358
TOTAL				0.448170333

This calculation is subjected to Pearson Correlation Co-efficient as stated in the below tables.

Table 5: Possible way of eradicating unskilled workers through the introduction of TVET training

S/N	Variables	SA (%)	A (%)	SD (%)	D (%)	U (%)	N (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
1.	TVET lecturer determines the students performance	77 (30.19)	102 (40.0)	26 (10.19)	26 (10.19)	24 (9.41)	255 (100)	3.7137	1.25820
2.	There are not available learning materials to TVET student's to acquire the required Knowledge	81 (31.76)	96 (37.64)	24 (9.41)	28 (18.27)	26 (10.19)	255 (100)	3.6863	1.30852
3	The problem of TVET is the technical workshop and the instructors handling the required skill determine the students interest on learning the skill	71 (27.84)	76 (29.80)	51 (20.00)	36 (14.11)	21 (8.23)	255 (100)	3.5490	1.25982
4	Independent variables Is there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need	90 (35.29)	60 (23.53)	24 (9.41)	32 (12.55)	49 (19.22)	255 (100)	3.4941	1.47651
5	does the cost of practical material adequate to the ability of learners to pay	143 (56.08)	50 (19.61)	13 (5.10)	22 (8.62)	27 (10.59)	255 (100)	4.0078	1.40301

Source: Researchers field Survey, 2023

		Correlations			
		TVET lecturers determines the students performance	There are not available learning materials to TVET student's to acquire the required Knowledge	The problem of TVET is the technical workshop and the instructors handling the required skill determine the students interest on learning the skill	Is there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need
Pearson Correlation	TVET lecturers determines the students performance	1.000	.814	.918	.800
	There are not available learning materials to TVET students to acquire the required Knowledge	.814	1.000	.920	.940
	The problem of TVET is the technical workshop and the instructors handling the required skill determine the students interest on learning the skill	.918	.920	1.000	.907
	Is there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need	.800	.940	.907	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	TVET lecturers determines the students performance	.	.000	.000	.000
	There are not available learning materials to TVET students to acquire the required Knowledge	.000	.	.000	.000
	The problem of TVET is the technical workshop and the instructors handling the required skill determine the students interest on learning the skill	.000	.000	.	.000
	Is there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need	.000	.000	.000	.
N	TVET lecturers determines the students performance	255	255	255	255
	There are not available learning materials to TVET students to acquire the required Knowledge	255	255	255	255
	The problem of TVET is the technical workshop and the instructors handling the required skill determine the students interest on learning the skill	255	255	255	255
	Is there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need	255	255	255	255

The correlations table above statistically indicates a strong association between TVET training and students performance with 91.8%, which establishes that TVET training as an indicator of students good performance significantly, correlates with potential Employee job performance respectively.

Model	Coefficients									
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	TVET lecturers determines the students performance									
	.415	.095		4.365	.000	.228	.602			
1	there any relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need									
	.823	.022	.918	36.796	.000	.779	.867	.918	.918	.918

a. Dependent Variable: TVET lecturers determines the students performance

The beta value in the coefficient table above suggests that student performance is significantly related to Lecturers readiness. By implication, a 1% change in readiness will lead to a corresponding increase in student performance by 91.8%. That is, the introduction and implementation of TVET curriculum to the present day societal need will significantly lead to increased lecturers readiness, etc. It, therefore, means that the relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need contributes immeasurably to enhancing lecturer’s readiness that will lead to students’ performance.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	341.683	3	113.894	473.155	.000 ^b
	Residual	60.419	251	.241		
	Total	402.102	254			

a. Dependent Variable: TVET lecturers determines the students performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), lecturers readiness, relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.922 ^a	.850	.848	.49062	.850	473.155	3	251	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), lecturers readiness, relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need

It can be deduced from the model summary, that holding other factors constant, lecturers readiness, relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need, using the adjusted R. Square value of 84.8%, suggesting that the changes in students performance is explained by lecturers readiness and the relevance of the TVET curriculum to the present day societal need. It implies that an increase with a focus on lectures readiness, TVET curriculum relevance, would significantly enhance students' performance

As shown in the coefficient table, the p-value of .000 ($p < 0.05$) shows there is a significant relationship between TVET knowledge to meet industry need. This is to say that there is strong association between TVET knowledge and changing world of work. Therefore, we accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses.

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